

Finite Element–Based Design and Stress Evaluation of a Pressure Vessel as per ASME BPVC

¹Sanket Uchade, ²Hitesh Gaikwad, ³Mansi Kadam, ⁴Nagareddy Gadlegaonkar

^{1, 2, 3, 4} Department of Mechanical Engineering, G.H. Rasoni College of Engineering and Management, Wagholi, Pune, Affiliated to Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune, India

Abstract- Pressure vessels are important equipment used for storing and handling fluids under pressure in industries such as oil and gas, chemical processing, and LPG storage. Because these vessels often contain hazardous materials, their design must ensure safe and reliable operation under different working conditions. In the present study, a vertical pressure vessel was designed based on the guidelines of ASME Boiler and Pressure Vessel Code Section VIII. A 3D model of the vessel was prepared and analyzed using ANSYS Workbench and SolidWorks Simulation software. Finite element analysis was carried out to examine stress distribution, deformation, and thermal effects produced during operation. The material properties used in the analysis include yield strength of 232 MPa and a Poisson's ratios of 0.3. These properties are applied during the simulation to determine stress distribution, deformation, and structural safety of the pressure vessel. The results indicated that the nozzle-to-shell junction and manway regions experienced higher stress concentration compared to other parts of the vessel. To improve the structural performance, a reinforcement pad was introduced around the nozzle area, which helped in reducing localized stresses and improving load transfer. The FEA results were then compared with analytical calculations, and both showed good agreement. The study confirms that the use of ASME design standards together with finite element analysis provides an effective approach for developing safe, durable, and cost-efficient pressure vessel designs.

Keywords- Pressure vessel design, ASME Section VIII Division 2, Finite Element Method (FEM), Stress distribution, Reinforcement pad (RF pad), Structural performance

1. Introduction

Pressure vessels are enclosed structures designed to store liquids or gases under pressures greater than atmospheric pressure. They are extensively used in industries such as oil and gas, chemical processing, power generation, and manufacturing plants where high-pressure systems are essential for operation. Since these vessels often contain hazardous or pressurized fluids, proper design and analysis are necessary to ensure safe and reliable performance during service.

The design of pressure vessels is generally based on standard engineering codes such as the ASME Boiler and Pressure Vessel Code, which provides guidelines for material selection, allowable stress limits, fabrication methods, and thickness calculations. While conventional analytical methods are useful for determining basic design parameters, they may not accurately predict localized stresses in critical areas like nozzle connections and welded joints. To overcome these limitations, Finite Element Analysis (FEA) is widely used to study stress distribution, deformation, and structural behavior under actual loading conditions.

In this study, a vertical pressure vessel is designed and analyzed using ASME code procedures together with FEA techniques. The objective of the work is to examine the stress pattern in the vessel, evaluate its structural performance, and improve the overall safety and reliability of the design under operating conditions. Figure 1 illustrates the pressure vessel model used for structural and thermal analysis.

Figure.1 Pressure Vessel

2. Objectives

- To design and develop a pressure vessel model according to ASME BPVC guidelines by considering suitable material properties and operating parameters.
- To carry out finite element analysis for structural, thermal, and fatigue conditions in order to study stress distribution, deformation, temperature influence, and overall structural behavior.
- To perform thermal analysis of the vertical pressure vessel for examining temperature variation through the vessel thickness.
- To verify and improve the pressure vessel design by comparing analytical calculations with FEA outcomes to achieve safe, reliable, and efficient performance.

3. Applications

Pressure vessel is the container for fluid under high pressure. They are used in variety of industries like:

- Petroleum refining
- Chemical plant
- Power plant
- Food and beverage
- Medical application
- LPG tanks and many more

A pressure vessel is a closed container designed to store liquids, vapors, or gases at pressures higher than atmospheric pressure. These vessels are widely used in many industrial sectors because they can safely handle fluids under high pressure and temperature conditions. Common applications of pressure vessels include petroleum refineries, chemical processing industries, power plants, food and beverage industries, medical systems, and LPG storage tanks. Table 1 presents the material properties used for the pressure vessel analysis.

Table.1 Material Properties

Location	Material	Modulus of Elasticity (GPa)	Yield Strength (MPa)	Allowable Stress (MPa)
Shell	SA-516Gr 70	195	232	138
Head				
Nozzle				
Support				

Pressure vessels are also extensively used in water treatment systems such as mixed bed exchangers, activated carbon filters, sand filters, and dual media filters. In many cases, carbon steel vessels with internal rubber lining are used to improve corrosion resistance and service life. Additional components such as strainers, screen laterals, ladders, and working platforms are often provided to support safe operation and maintenance of the system.

Materials of the pressure vessel:

Choosing the proper material for a pressure vessel is an important part of the design process because it affects the strength, durability, safety, and operating life of the equipment. Pressure vessels are subjected to internal pressure, temperature variation, and sometimes corrosive fluids, so the selected material must be capable of withstanding these conditions without failure during service.

The material selection process is generally carried out according to recognized standards such as the ASME Boiler and Pressure Vessel Code. These standards provide information related to material specifications, allowable stress values, and design limitations to ensure safe and reliable operation of the vessel under different working conditions.

a) Mechanical Strength and Creep Resistance

The material must possess adequate mechanical strength to resist internal pressure, external loads, and thermal stresses. Key properties include:

- Yield Strength – Determines the stress level at which permanent deformation begins
- Ultimate Tensile Strength (UTS) – Indicates maximum load-carrying capacity
- Allowable Stress – Derived from safety factors as per design codes

For high-temperature applications, creep resistance becomes essential. Creep is the time-dependent deformation that occurs under constant stress at elevated temperatures. Materials must also have:

- Creep rupture strength – Ability to withstand stress over long durations without failure
- Stability of microstructure at operating temperature

Common materials used:

- Carbon steels (for moderate conditions)
- Low alloy steels (for elevated temperature service)
- Stainless steels (for combined strength and corrosion resistance)

b) Corrosion and Chemical Resistance

Pressure vessels often contain reactive fluids, hydrocarbons, or corrosive chemicals, making corrosion resistance a major selection factor. Corrosion can lead to:

- Wall thinning
- Crack initiation
- Sudden catastrophic failure

Types of corrosion to consider:

- Uniform corrosion
- Pitting corrosion
- Stress corrosion cracking (SCC)
- Hydrogen embrittlement

Material selection strategies include:

- Using corrosion-resistant alloys (e.g., stainless steel, nickel alloys)

- Applying protective coatings or linings
- Providing corrosion allowance in design thickness

For example, vessels handling hydrocarbon + water mixtures may require materials resistant to H₂S corrosion or chloride attack.

c) Fracture Toughness and Brittle Failure Prevention

Fracture toughness is a measure of a material's ability to resist crack propagation. This is especially critical in pressure vessels operating at:

- Low temperatures (risk of brittle fracture)
- High stress concentrations (e.g., weld joints, nozzles)

Materials with poor toughness may fail suddenly without warning. Therefore:

- Ductile materials are preferred for safety
- Impact testing (Charpy V-notch test) is often required
- Design codes specify minimum design metal temperature (MDMT)

Proper material selection ensures resistance against brittle fracture even under extreme conditions.

d) Fabrication and Weldability

Pressure vessels are typically manufactured from rolled plates and welded sections, so the material must support efficient fabrication processes. Important factors include:

- Ductility – Allows forming, bending, and rolling without cracking
- Weldability – Ensures strong, defect-free joints
- Machinability – Facilitates nozzle and flange preparation

Poor weldability can lead to:

- Residual stresses
- Weld defects (porosity, cracking)
- Reduced fatigue life

Materials like carbon steel (e.g., SA-516) are widely used because they offer a good balance of strength, weldability, and cost.

e) Thermal Properties and Expansion

Materials must handle temperature gradients and thermal cycling without failure. Key considerations:

- Coefficient of thermal expansion
- Thermal conductivity
- Resistance to thermal fatigue

Mismatch in thermal expansion (especially in composite or lined vessels) can induce additional stresses.

f) Economic and Availability Considerations

Even if a material meets all technical requirements, it must also be:

- Economically viable
- Readily available in required sizes and forms
- Compatible with fabrication facilities

Engineers often perform cost vs performance optimization to select the most practical material.

g) Typical Materials Used in Pressure Vessels

Common material categories include:

- Carbon Steel – Economical, widely used (moderate conditions)

- Low Alloy Steel – Improved strength and temperature resistance
- Stainless Steel – Excellent corrosion resistance
- Nickel Alloys – Used in highly corrosive environments
- Composite Materials – Used in specialized lightweight applications

4. Methodology

Finite Element Modeling and Analysis Process of Pressure Vessel

Finite Element Analysis (FEA) is widely used to study the structural behavior of pressure vessels under different operating conditions. In this work, SOLIDWORKS Simulation and ANSYS Workbench are used for modeling and analysis of the vertical pressure vessel. The finite element method predicts deformation, strain, and stress developed in the vessel when subjected to internal pressure, thermal loading, and external forces. The geometry is divided into smaller elements such as tetrahedral, shell, or beam elements, and numerical calculations are performed using appropriate solvers to obtain accurate results.

SOLIDWORKS Simulation provides different analysis approaches including three-dimensional, two-dimensional, plane stress, plane strain, and axisymmetric modeling options. Adaptive meshing techniques are also available to improve convergence and solution accuracy. For thin structures, shell meshing can be automatically generated to simplify the analysis and reduce computational effort.

The pressure vessel design and structural assessment are carried out using both analytical calculations and finite element analysis. The analytical design follows the ASME Boiler and Pressure Vessel Code, while FEA is used to evaluate detailed stress distribution and deformation under actual loading conditions. This combined approach helps in validating the design and identifying critical stress regions that may not be accurately predicted using conventional calculations alone.

The three-dimensional geometry of the pressure vessel is developed using ANSYS Space Claim and analyzed in ANSYS 2022 R2. ASME-grade carbon steel is selected as the vessel material because of its good strength, weldability, and suitability for moderate pressure applications. The material properties used in the analysis include a yield strength of 232 MPa and a Poisson's ratio of 0.3.

1) Design and Analysis Codes

The pressure vessel is designed according to the ASME Boiler and Pressure Vessel Code to ensure safe and reliable operation. ASME Section VIII Division 1 is used for basic design calculations and component sizing, while ASME Section VIII Division 2 is referred to for detailed stress evaluation using finite element analysis. Division 1 provides standard design equations, whereas Division 2 supports advanced stress assessment and design verification.

2) Analytical Design Calculations

The minimum required shell thickness is calculated using ASME design equations based on internal pressure conditions.

$$t = \frac{PD}{2SE - 0.2P}$$

Where:

- t = Required shell thickness
- P = Internal pressure
- D = Internal diameter of vessel

- S = Allowable stress
- E = Weld joint efficiency

This equation ensures that the vessel wall thickness is sufficient to withstand internal pressure safely. Additional calculations are performed for heads, nozzles, flanges, and support structures.

3) Design Considerations and Safety Factors

a) Corrosion Allowance

Extra thickness is provided to compensate for material loss caused by corrosion during service life, helping maintain long-term structural integrity.

b) Weld Joint Efficiency

Weld joint efficiency accounts for the quality of welded connections. Higher efficiency values are assigned to fully inspected welds, while lower values are used for partially inspected welds.

c) Safety Margin

ASME allowable stress values include safety margins to prevent yielding, fatigue failure, and bursting under operating conditions.

d) Operating Conditions

The design also considers factors such as maximum allowable working pressure, operating temperature, and cyclic loading effects during service.

4) Material Selection

The material selection process considers strength, weldability, corrosion resistance, availability, and cost. Carbon steel is selected because it offers sufficient mechanical strength, good fabrication properties, and economical advantages for moderate-pressure applications.

5) Finite Element Analysis Procedure

a) Pre-Processing

The CAD model is imported into ANSYS Workbench after geometry creation in ANSYS Space Claim. Unnecessary geometric details are removed to improve mesh quality and reduce solution time. Material properties such as elastic modulus, yield strength, and Poisson's ratio are assigned before meshing. Finer mesh refinement is applied near nozzle regions, supports, and other stress concentration areas.

b) Boundary Conditions and Loading

Different loading conditions are applied to represent actual operating conditions. Internal pressure is applied uniformly on the inner surfaces of the vessel. Additional effects such as self-weight, wind loading, and thermal loads are included when required. Fixed support conditions are applied at the skirt support region to simulate actual mounting conditions.

c) Solution and Analysis

The solver calculates Von Mises stress, deformation, displacement, and support reactions. Critical regions such as nozzle-to-shell junctions and welded areas are carefully evaluated and compared with allowable stress limits specified in ASME standards.

6) Validation and Result Interpretation

The analytical calculations are compared with FEA results to validate the pressure vessel design. Regions with higher stress concentration are identified, especially around nozzles and weld joints. If stress values exceed permissible limits, design modifications such as reinforcement pads or thickness

changes are introduced. Mesh refinement and boundary condition checks are also carried out to improve result accuracy and reliability.

7) Software and Simulation Platform

a) Geometry Modeling

ANSYS Space Claim is used for creating the three-dimensional geometry of the pressure vessel according to ASME design standards and calculated dimensions.

b) Simulation Procedure

The prepared CAD model is transferred to ANSYS Workbench for analysis. Geometry cleanup is performed before meshing to remove unwanted features. Suitable mesh density and element types are selected to improve solution accuracy. After solving, post-processing tools are used to obtain stress contours, deformation plots, and safety evaluation results for the pressure vessel.

5. Finite Element Analysis Procedure

i) Geometry Import

The simulation process begins by importing the CAD model into the ANSYS Workbench environment. The pressure vessel geometry is generally created using software such as ANSYS Space Claim or other CAD applications and then transferred to ANSYS for further analysis and simulation setup.

ii) Geometry Preparation (CAD Cleanup)

Once the geometry is imported, the model is prepared for analysis by removing unnecessary details such as very small fillets, unwanted edges, overlaps, gaps, and extra surfaces. These features may not influence the final results but can create difficulties during meshing and increase computation time. Proper geometry cleanup improves mesh quality, enhances solution accuracy, and helps achieve a more stable simulation process.

iii) Simulation and Analysis

After geometry preparation, the analysis procedure is carried out in ANSYS through a sequence of steps. Material properties are assigned, boundary conditions and loads are applied, and the model is discretized using meshing techniques. The solver then performs the numerical calculations to determine stresses, deformation, temperature distribution, or other required results. Finally, the obtained results are evaluated and interpreted. The overall procedure may differ depending on whether the analysis is structural, thermal, or fluid-related.

6. Implementation

For the structural analysis, the three-dimensional pressure vessel model was meshed using the SOLID185 element available in ANSYS Workbench. SOLID185 is an eight-node three-dimensional solid element, where each node has three translational degrees of freedom along the x, y, and z directions. This element is suitable for analysing solid structures subjected to pressure, thermal loading, and mechanical forces, making it appropriate for pressure vessel applications.

The SOLID185 element can also handle nonlinear conditions such as plastic deformation, creep, stress stiffening, and large strain effects. Because of these capabilities, it is widely used for structural components where accurate stress evaluation is important.

During meshing, proper attention was given to element quality and mesh distribution to achieve reliable results. A structured or semi-structured mesh pattern was used wherever possible to improve solution

accuracy and convergence. Parameters such as aspect ratio, skewness, and element distortion were checked to maintain acceptable mesh quality. Finer mesh refinement was provided near critical regions such as nozzle connections, fillets, supports, and other stress concentration areas to capture detailed stress variation accurately. Table 2 summarizes the equivalent stress values obtained from the finite element analysis of the pressure vessel.

Care was also taken to maintain proper node connectivity and element orientation in order to avoid numerical errors such as distorted or zero-volume elements. Mesh refinement studies were considered to ensure that further mesh improvement did not significantly affect the final results, confirming the accuracy and stability of the analysis. Figure 2 shows the finite element model of the pressure vessel developed for numerical analysis.

Overall, the meshing approach using SOLID185 provided a suitable balance between computational efficiency and analysis accuracy for the pressure vessel simulation.

1) Material Definition

Material properties were assigned according to ASME Boiler and Pressure Vessel Code Section II Part D. Properties such as elastic modulus, density, Poisson's ratio, yield strength, and thermal characteristics were defined in ANSYS Workbench. Temperature-dependent properties were included wherever necessary for thermal analysis.

2) Meshing

A finer mesh was generated in critical locations such as nozzle-to-shell junctions and support regions where higher stresses were expected. At least three elements were maintained through the shell thickness to improve the accuracy of stress and deformation results. Proper mesh quality was maintained throughout the model to obtain stable and reliable solutions.

3) Loading and Boundary Conditions

- Internal Pressure:

Internal pressure was applied uniformly on the inner surfaces of the vessel to simulate operating cond.

- Compensating Force

Compensating forces were considered to balance external effects and maintain structural stability.

- Nozzle Load:

Forces and moments acting on nozzles due to connected piping systems were included in the analysis.

- Self-Weight

The weight of the vessel and attached components due to gravity was considered during simulation.

- Convection

Convection boundary conditions were applied to study heat transfer through the insulation and surrounding environment.

- Temperature

Thermal loading was included to evaluate temperature effects and thermal stresses in the vessel structure.

- Fixed supports.

Fixed support conditions were applied at the support locations to restrict movement and represent actual mounting conditions.

Table.2 Summary of Equivalent Stresses

Sr. No.	Component	Induced Stress (MPa)	Allowable Stress Limit (MPa)
1	Nozzle 1	150.1	138
2	Nozzle 2	157.85	138
3	Nozzle 3	157.84	138
4	Nozzle 4 nozzle 4</td <td>150.32</td> <td>138</td>	150.32	138

Figure 2. Finite Element Model

7. Result and Discussion

The structural analysis carried out in ANSYS Workbench shows that the von Mises stress is not evenly distributed over the entire pressure vessel. Higher stress values are mainly observed at the nozzle-to-shell junction because this region experiences stress concentration due to changes in geometry, internal pressure, nozzle loading, and thermal effects. Increased stress is also noticed near welded regions and support areas where boundary conditions and thickness variations affect the stress pattern. These critical locations require proper reinforcement and smooth structural transitions to reduce stress concentration and improve the safety of the vessel. The obtained stress values are compared with the allowable limits specified in ASME Boiler and Pressure Vessel Code Section II Part D to verify the structural safety of the design. The analysis demonstrates that finite element analysis is useful for identifying critical regions and evaluating the structural performance of the pressure vessel under operating conditions.

Result Verification: Comparison of Analytical and FEA Results

Self-Weight Reaction Check

The reaction force due to self-weight is verified using analytical calculation and FEA results.

Given:

- Mass = 69200 kg
- Acceleration due to gravity = 9.81 m/s^2

The reaction force is calculated as:

$$F = m \times g$$

$$F = 69200 \times 9.81$$

$$F = 678852 \text{ N}$$

Tabular Data				
Time [s]	Force Reaction (X) [N]	Force Reaction (Y) [N]	Force Reaction (Z) [N]	Force Reaction (Total) [N]
1 1.	3.8776e-005	6.7878e+005	-9.1646e-005	6.7878e+005

Figure 3. Reaction Force Components and Total Reaction Force

The analytical reaction force obtained is 678852 N, while the vertical reaction force from FEA is 678780 N. Both values are very close, which confirms that the self-weight reaction check is verified successfully. Figure 3 illustrates the reaction force components and the total reaction force obtained from the finite element analysis of the pressure vessel.

Hoop Stress Check

Given:

- Internal pressure, $P = 1.7 \text{ MPa}$
- Internal radius of shell, $r = 1378 \text{ mm}$
- Shell thickness, $t = 37 \text{ mm}$

For a thin pressure vessel, the hoop stress is calculated using:

$$\sigma_h = \frac{Pr}{t}$$

Substituting the values:

$$\sigma_h = \frac{1.7 \times 1378}{37}$$

$$\sigma_h = 63.31 \text{ MPa}$$

The average hoop stress obtained from FEA is 63.32 MPa. The analytical and FEA results are nearly identical, confirming the accuracy of the analysis and validating the hoop stress calculation. Figure 4 shows the hoop stress distribution developed in the pressure vessel under internal pressure loading.

Figure 4. Hoop Stress

8. Conclusion

The finite element analysis indicated that the stress values at nozzles N1, N2, N3, and N4 were higher than the allowable limits. The highest stresses were mainly observed near the nozzle-to-shell connections because of stress concentration caused by external loading and sudden changes in geometry.

To reduce these stresses, an external reinforcement pad (RF pad) was provided around the nozzle regions. The reinforcement pad increases the thickness and stiffness of the junction area, allowing the applied loads to spread more uniformly over the surrounding shell surface. This helps in lowering the stress concentration near the welded connections and reduces local deformation. Table 3 presents the details of stress evaluation before and after the incorporation of reinforcement (RF) pads in the pressure vessel nozzles.

After introducing the RF pad, the stress distribution improved significantly, and the stress values were reduced to within the allowable limits specified by ASME Boiler and Pressure Vessel Code Section II Part D. The reinforcement also improved the overall structural strength and stability of the nozzle connections under operating conditions.

Table 3. Details Modification of stress evaluation

Sr. No.	Component	Without RF Pad Stress (MPa)	With RF Pad Stress (MPa)	Allowable Stress Limit (MPa)
1	Nozzle 1	150.1	116.86	138
2	Nozzle 2	157.85	117.76	138
3	Nozzle 3	157.84	118.12	138
4	Nozzle 4	150.32	120.68	138

References

- 1) Sowiński, K. Application and Accuracy of Shell Theory in the Analysis of Stress and Deformations in Cylindrical Pressure Vessels. *Thin-Walled Struct.* 2023, 188, 110826. [CrossRef]
- 2) Devaraju, A.; Pazhanivel, K. A study on stress analysis for design of pressure vessel. *Int. J. Mech. Prod. Eng.* 2015, 3, 98–101.
- 3) Patel, N.R.; Vasava, A.; Vasava, J.; Patel, S. Design and analysis of pressure vessel amalgamating with selection of material used in marine application. *Int. J. Innov. Res. Sci. Eng. Technol.* 2013, 2, 2035–2042.
- 4) Prasanth, D.; Sachidananda, H. Design and analysis of pressure vessel. *Int. J. Mech. Prod. Eng. Res. Dev.* 2019, 9, 125–136.
- 5) Mali, A.; Bhosale, H.; Singh Bedi, D.; Modasara, A. A Review Paper on Study of Pressure Vessel, Design and Analysis. *Int. Res. J.Eng. Technol.* 2017, 4, 1369–1374.
- 6) The American Society of Mechanical Engineers. SECTION VIII Rules for Construction of Pressure Vessels 2019 ASME Boiler and Pressure Vessel Code an International Code; The American Society of Mechanical Engineers: New York, NY, USA, 2019.2, 28–34.
- 7) Talu, S.; Talu, M. Algorithm for Optimal Design of Pressurized Toroidal LPG Fuel Tanks with Constant Section Described by Imposed Algebraic Plane Curves. *Hidraulica* 2018, 2, 14–20.

- 8) M. Azeem, et al., "Influence of winding angles on hoop stress in composite pressure vessels: Finite element analysis", *Results in Engineering*, 23 (2024), 101667.
- 9) Gadlegaonkar N, Bansod PJ, Lakshmikanthan A, Bhole K. Review on additively manufactured AlSi10Mg alloy. *Journal of Mines, Metals and Fuels*. 2025;73(1):87–101.
- 10) J. Monteiro, S. Y. Nayak, K. A. Mathias, and N. Patil, "Effect of fiber orientation and reinforcements on the performance of composite pressure vessel using finite element analysis, *Cogent Engineering*, 11(1) (2024).
- 11) Gophane, N. Dharashivkar, P. Mulik, and P. Patil, "Theoretical and finite element analysis of pressure vessel", *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 17(12) (2024), 1148-1158.
- 12) Hiremath, S., Kumar, N., & Nagareddy, G. (2016). Linear and static analysis using FEA of various nozzle-to-shell junctions of a pressure vessel.
- 13) Sowiński, K. Application and Accuracy of Shell Theory in the Analysis of Stress and Deformations in Cylindrical Pressure Vessels. *Thin-Walled Struct.* 2023, 188, 110826.
- 14) Devaraju, A.; Pazhanivel, K. A study on stress analysis for design of pressure vessel. *Int. J. Mech. Prod. Eng.* 2015, 3, 98–101.
- 15) Patel, N.R.; Vasava, A.; Vasava, J.; Patel, S. Design and analysis of pressure vessel amalgamating with selection of material used in marine application. *Int. J. Innov. Res. Sci. Eng. Technol.* 2013, 2, 2035–2042.
- 16) Prasanth, D.; Sachidananda, H. Design and analysis of pressure vessel. *Int. J. Mech. Prod. Eng. Res. Dev.* 2019, 9, 125–136.
- 17) Mali, A.; Bhosale, H.; Singh Bedi, D.; Modasara, A. A Review Paper on Study of Pressure Vessel, Design and Analysis. *Int. Res. J. Eng. Technol.* 2017, 4, 1369–1374.
- 18) The American Society of Mechanical Engineers. SECTION VIII R Ules for Construction of Pressure Vessels 2019 ASME Boiler and Pressure Vessel Code an International Code; The American Society of Mechanical Engineers: New York, NY, USA, 2019.
- 19) Pendbhaje, A.R.; Gaikwad, M.; Deshmukh, N.; Patil, R. Design and analysis of pressure vessel. *Int. J. Innov. Res. Technol. Sci.* 2014, 2, 28–34.
- 20) Talu, S.; Talu, M. Algorithm for Optimal Design of Pressurized Toroidal LPG Fuel Tanks with Constant Section Described by Imposed Algebraic Plane Curves. *Hidraulica* 2018, 2, 14–20.
- 21) De Wilde, W.P.; Blain, W.R.; Brebbia, C.A. (Eds.) *Advances in Composite Materials and Structures VII; Structures and Materials*; WIT: Southampton, UK; Boston, MA, USA, 2000; ISBN 978-1-85312-825-7.
- 22) Gadlegaonkar N, Bansod PJ, Lakshmikanthan A, Bhole K, Patel GCM, Reddy NC, et al. Corrosion studies of SLM printed AlSi10Mg parts. *Archives of Foundry Engineering*. 2025;25(3):179–188.
- 23) Shen, J.; Tang, Y.F.; Liu, Y.H. Buckling Analysis of Pressure Vessel Based on Finite Element Method. *Procedia Eng.* 2015, 130, 355–363.
- 24) Majumder H, Gajghate SS, Sahu AR, Behera AK, Limbadri C, Ukey K. Finite element analysis of wheel rim by additive manufacturing materials. *Materials Today: Proceedings*. 2023 May 30.